

Synthesis and Spectral Characterization of Schiff Base Complexes of Cu(II)

O. P. ARORA* and SUDHINDRA N. MISRA

Department of Chemistry, University of Jodhpur, Jodhpur-342 001

and

M. P. BHUTRA

Department of Physics, University of Jodhpur, Jodhpur-342 001

Manuscript received 23 October 1979, accepted 30 December 1979

Six new complexes with Schiff bases derived from the *bis* (ethylacetoacetato) Cu(II) have been prepared and characterized by elemental analysis magnetic measurements electronic & I. R. Spectra. All these studies indicate that the complexes most probably have distorted octahedral structure.

A large number of metal complexes of Schiff base have been reported in literature¹-including those with Cu(II)². We report here the result of our studies on the complexes of Cu(II) with Schiff base *bis* (vanillin) ethylenediamine, (Van-en), *bis* (Vanillin) propylenediimine (Van-pn), *bis* (Vanillin) benzidine (van-ben), *bis* Vanillin-O-phenylene diimine (Van-O-phen), Vanillin α -naphthylimine (Van- α naph); *bis* (Vanillin) thiosemi-carbazone (Van-tscz).

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade Diaquo *bis* (ethylacetoacetato) Cu(II)³ and Schiff bases⁴ were prepared as per method given in literature.

Preparation of Complexes

The addition of diaquo *bis* (ethylacetoacetato) copper(II) (0.01M) dissolved in the chloroform to the solution of Schiff base *bis* (Vanillin) ethylenediimine (0.01M) in ethanol resulted in the separation of dark yellow precipitate. The compound was filtered, washed with ether and dried in vacuum at room temperature.

In case of Schiff bases e.g. *bis* (Vanillin) propylenediimine, Vanillin- α naphthylimine and *bis* (Vanillin) O-phenylenediimine no precipitation was occurred on mixing the reactants at room temperature. Hence the reaction mixture was refluxed for an hour and volume was reduced to one third. The solution thus obtained was kept for slow crystallization in dessicator. Within three to four days crystalline compound was obtained. The product was washed with ether and dried in vacco (yield 78-88%).

The compounds were found soluble in coordinating solvents e.g. dimethyl sulfoxide and dimethyl formamide while sparingly soluble in methanol and ethanol.

Analysis

Copper was estimated by standard method and nitrogen by kjeldahl method. The result of the analysis are shown in Table 1.

Physical measurement :

The electronic spectra of all the complexes in DMF were obtained with Carl-Zeiss VSU-2 spectrophotometer. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were made in solution using Gouy method at 25°. The I. R. spectra of the complexes in KBr pellet were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 521-Spectrophotometer in the region 4000-400 cm⁻¹.

Result and Discussion

Results given in the Table-1 shows that complexes have the composition 1 : 1. The value of magnetic moment (μ_{eff}) of these complexes are in the range of 1.82-1.92 BM. Suggesting the presence of one unpaired electron and hence the complexes are spin free with octahedral stereochemistry.

The absorption spectra of the complexes is characterized by two band maxima in the region 705-740 nm and 815-865 nm (Table 1) which also supported the distorted octahedral species of Cu(II) complexes^{5,6} studies on electronic spectra of Cu(II)⁷ indicate that the three transitions : $2D_1 \nu^2 A_1(\nu_1) \rightarrow 2A_1$, (ν_1) , $2D_1 \rightarrow 2D_2$ (ν_2), $2D_1 \rightarrow 2E$ (ν_3) close in energy are found, it might be due distortion caused by the non identical nature of coordinating atoms diminishing the ν_1 band.

*For correspondence.

TABLE 1—ANALYSIS, MELTING POINTS, MAGNETIC MOMENT AND ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL OF Cu(II) COMPLEXES

S. No.	Compounds	MP° (°C)	Copper		Nitrogen		Sulphur		μ_{eff} BM.	Electronic Spectra	
			calc	found	calc	found	calc	found		ν_2	ν_3
1.	Cu(EAA) ₂ (Van-en)	182 d	9.77	9.3	4.30	4.1	-	-	1.82	720 nm	825 nm
2.	Cu(EAA) ₂ (Van-O-phen)	-	9.10	8.7	4.01	4.0	-	-	1.85	705 nm	815 nm
3.	Cu(EAA) ₂ (Van-ben)	300	8.20	8.8	3.61	3.1	-	-	1.87	740 nm	865 nm
4.	Cu(EAA) ₂ (Van- α -naph)(H ₂ O)	140-145	10.29	9.8	2.26	2.2	-	-	1.88	735 nm	855 nm
5.	Cu(EAA) ₂ (Van-Pn)	220	9.56	9.8	4.21	4.3	-	-	1.84	725 nm	840 nm
6.	Cu(EAA) ₂ (Van-tscz)	147 d	9.32	9.3	6.16	5.8	4.70	4.9	1.92	715 nm	855 nm

TABLE 2—SIGNIFICANT I. R. VIBRATIONAL FREQUENCIES AND THEIR TENTATIVE ASSIGNMENTS

Complexes	$\nu_{\text{C=O}}$	$\nu_{\text{C=N}}$	$\nu_{\text{C-N}}$	Assignment Frequency CM ⁻¹				
				$\nu_{\text{C-O}}$	Phenolic -OH	$\nu_{\text{C-N}}$	$\nu_{\text{C=C}}$	$\nu_{\text{Cu-N}}$
Cu(EAA) ₂ (Van-en)	1715w	1665s	1575s	1500s	1275s	1020m	1450m	435s
Cu(EAA) ₂ (Van-O-phen)	1720w	1665s	1590s	1500s	1285s	1025s	1450w	450wbr
Cu(EAA) ₂ (Van-ben)	1720w	1675w	1585s	1495s	1285s	1025w	1445w	445m
Cu(EAA) ₂ (Van- α -Naph)(H ₂ O)	1710w	1665s	1590s	1500s	1280s	1020s	1450m	455s
Cu(EAA) ₂ (Van-Pn)	1720w	1665s	1580s	1490w	1280s	1020m	1450wbr	440m
Cu(EAA) ₂ (Van-tscz)	1705w	1665s	1580s	1495s	1280s	1020s	1460w	445w

The band attributable to Intra molecular hydrogen bonded off has not disappeared in the complexes⁸. This indicate the OH of the ligand has not taken part in the complex formation. The elemental analysis support the above statement (Table 2).

A strong band around 1590 cm⁻¹ is assigned to the C=N stretch of the free Schiff base and that found in the region 1665-1675 cm⁻¹ for the complexes. This frequency Schiff suggests the coordination through the azomethine group⁹.

The characteristic band due to the C=O and C=C of the *bis* (ethylacetoacetato) copper(II) found at 1600 cm⁻¹ and 1525 cm⁻¹ ¹⁰ respectively. Former one shifts to higher frequencies where as the latter one shifts to lower frequencies on complexation. Bands appearing in the region 1720-1450 cm⁻¹ are difficult to assign as various bands fall in this region. However, the bands have been assigned tantetively comparing the spectra of respective ligand.

Metal nitrogen stretching vibration also appear in the region 455-435 cm⁻¹ in all the complexes. This band either does not shift or shifts slightly on substitution in ligand. Other Cu-N bands fall beyond the range of instrument. This supports the coordination of nitrogen to metal.

The above spectral and magnetic study suggests the distorted octahedral symmetry of the complexes under study.

Acknowledgement

Authors are grateful to Prof. R.C. Kapoor, Head, Department of Chemistry, University of Jodhpur, Jodhpur for providing the facilities.

References

1. R. H. HOLM, G. W. EVERETT (JR) and A. CHAKRAVERTY, Progress in Inorganic Chemistry, edited by F. A. COTTON (Interscience, New York) 1966, 7, 83.
2. WILLIAM E. HATFIELD "Transition metal Chemistry Vol. 5 Edited by R. L. CARLIN 1969, 47.
3. R. L. BELFORD, A. E. MARTELL and M. CALVIN, *J. Inorg Nuclear Chem.*, 1956, 2, 11.
4. FAKHRUL HASAN RIZVI and NASEER AHMAD, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, 54, 1084.
5. J. I. BULLOCK and S. L. JOHNES, *J. Chem. Soc.*, (A)1971, 2351.
6. NARAYAN S. BHAVE and R. B. KHARAT, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, 56, 244.
7. C. A. AGAMBER and K. G. ORREL, *J. Chem. Soc.*, (A) 1969, 897.
8. H. H. FREEDMAN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 83, 2900.
9. N. S. BIRADAR and U. H. KULKARNI, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1971, 33, 3847.
10. R. W. HAY and B. P. CAUGHLEY, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1967, 20, 1829.